

INTERACTION OF SULPHURYL CHLORIDE WITH ARYLAMIDES OF AROMATIC ACIDS. PART II. ORIENTING INFLUENCES OF GROUPS IN SUBS- TITUTION REACTIONS IN AROMATIC COMPOUNDS.

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Sulphuryl chloride gives chloro derivatives with arylamides of salicylic acid, having chlorine both in the acidic and the basic parts of the molecule. Varying proportions of sulphuryl chloride show that chlorine enters first in position *para* to OH and *para* to NHCOR, then *ortho* to OH and then *ortho* to NHCOR according to the nature of the reacting amide. With arylamides of *o*-methoxy- and *o*-chlorobenzoic acids and *o*-toluic acid, products with chlorine only in the basic part are obtained. The constitution of compounds is proved by hydrolysis and synthesis.

It is known that the ease with which an incoming group enters a substituted benzene nucleus as well as the position which the new substituent would take, depend upon the nature of the substituent already present and the reagent used for substitution. It has also been generally accepted that the substituents such as OH, NH₂, CH₃ and halogens are mainly *ortho* and *para* directing and the order of their reactivity is OH > NH₂ > halogens > CH₃ and the substituents such as COOH, SO₃H and NO₂ are predominantly *meta* directing, their order of reactivity being NO₂ > SO₃H > COOH.

The present work concerns the reaction of sulphuryl chloride with arylamides of salicylic, *o*-methoxybenzoic, *o*-toluic and *o*-chlorobenzoic acids.

It has been observed in Part I (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1938, 15, 649) that chlorine always enters the basic part of the molecule in the case of simple benzoic acid derivatives, but the introduction of the OH group in benzene ring increases the reactivity of the acidic part of the molecule and substitution first takes place in the acidic part of the molecule. It has been observed that even when the reacting substances are in the molecular proportion of 1:1 in the case of salicylanilide and salicyl-*m*-toluidide, two products are obtained, *viz.*,

(1) 5-Chlorosalicylanilide and (2) 5-chlorosalicyl-4'-chloroanilide and
(1) 5-chlorosalicyl-*m*-toluidide and (2) 5-chlorosalicyl-6'-chloro-*m*-toluidide

(Me=1'), in the ratio of 1:9 and 1:4 respectively, showing thereby that the *para* directing influence of OH is stronger than that of NHCOR. In the case of salicyl-*o*-toluidide and salicyl-*p*-toluidide, 5-chlorosalicyl-5'-chloro-*o*-toluidide and 5-chlorosalicyl-*p*-toluidide (Me=1') are obtained when the reacting materials are in the molecular ratio of 1:1.

When two molecules of sulphuryl chloride are used for one of the amide, the dichloro compounds as above are obtained except in the case of salicyl-*p*-toluidide when no disubstitution product is formed.

Chlorination of the acidic part of the molecule does not take place in the case of the arylamides of *o*-methoxybenzoic acid, *o*-toluic acid and *o*-chlorobenzoic acid, which indicates that the directing power of NHCOR is stronger than that of OCH₃, CH₃ or chlorine.

In the case of *o*-tolu-*m*-toluidide, however, *o*-tolu-4:6-dichloro-*m*-toluidide (Me=1) is formed even when the reacting substances are in the molecular ratio of 1:1 and substitution products are formed in the case of *o*-chlorobenz-*o*-chloroanilide and *o*-chlorobenz-*p*-chloroanilide.

EXPERIMENTAL.

Sulphuryl chloride was gradually added to the amide suspended in dry benzene (about 40 c.c. for 5 g. of the amide) and the mixture, protected from moisture, was boiled under reflux for about 4-5 hours. After the removal of benzene, the reaction product was washed free from sulphuryl chloride with dry petroleum ether. The substances, generally soluble in benzene, alcohol and acetic acid, crystallised from alcohol in colourless needles. Mixtures were separated by fractional crystallisation from alcohol.

The constitution of substances marked (A) was proved by hydrolysis to known amines and acids and also by synthesis (by heating a mixture of the amine, acid and phosphorus trichloride at 120° for about 1 hour).

Substances marked (B) were identified by hydrolysis to the corresponding amines and acids only. In case of substances marked (D) in addition to (A) and (B), the amines were identified through their acetyl derivatives.

Hydrolysis was carried out by heating the substance in a sealed tube with 10-15% caustic potash solution in 50% alcohol at 170° for about 6 hours.

The compounds are described in Table I.

TABLE I.

Amide.	Mol. prop. of amide to SO ₂ Cl ₂ .	Product.	M. p.	Formula.	Found.	Required.	Yield.
Salicylanilide	1 : 1	(i) 5-Chlorosalicylanilide (A & D)	203-4°	C ₁₃ H ₁₀ O ₂ NCl	Cl, 14.3%	Cl, 14.3%	7%
		(ii) 5-Chlorosalicyl-4'-chloroanilide (B & D)	215-16°	C ₁₃ H ₉ O ₂ NCl ₂	Cl, 25.1	Cl, 25.2	63
Salicylanilide	1 : 2	5-Chlorosalicyl-4'-chloroanilide*	215-16°	C ₁₃ H ₉ O ₂ NCl ₂	—	—	80
Salicylanilide	1 : 4	(i) 5-Chlorosalicyl-4'-chloroanilide*	215°	C ₁₃ H ₉ O ₂ NCl ₂	—	—	45
		(ii) 3 : 5-Dichlorosalicyl-2' : 4'-dichloroanilide (B & D)	174-75°	C ₁₃ H ₇ O ₂ NCl ₄	Cl, 40.2 N, 4.2	Cl, 40.5 N, 4.0	13
Salicyl- <i>o</i> -toluidide	1 : 1	5-Chlorosalicyl-5'-chloro- <i>o</i> -toluidide (B&D)	171-72°	C ₁₄ H ₁₁ O ₂ NCl ₂	Cl, 23.8	Cl, 23.99	60
Salicyl- <i>o</i> -toluidide	1 : 2	5-Chlorosalicyl-5'-chloro- <i>o</i> -toluidide*	171-72°	C ₁₄ H ₁₁ O ₂ NCl ₂	—	—	90
Salicyl- <i>o</i> -toluidide	1 : 4	(i) 3 : 5-Dichlorosalicyl-5'-chloro- <i>o</i> -toluidide (B&D)	197-98°	C ₁₄ H ₁₀ O ₂ NCl ₃	31.9	32.2	10
		(ii) 5-Chlorosalicyl-5'-chloro- <i>o</i> -toluidide*	170-71°	C ₁₄ H ₁₁ O ₂ NCl ₂	—	—	40
Salicyl- <i>m</i> -toluidide	1 : 1	(i) 5-Chlorosalicyl- <i>m</i> -toluidide (C)	144-45°	C ₁₄ H ₁₂ O ₂ NCl	13.8	13.6	10
		(ii) 5-Chlorosalicyl-6'-chloro- <i>m</i> -toluidide (B)	221-22°	C ₁₄ H ₁₁ O ₂ NCl ₂	24.2	23.99	40
Salicyl- <i>m</i> -toluidide	1 : 2	5-Chlorosalicyl-6'-chloro- <i>m</i> -toluidide*	221-22°	C ₁₄ H ₁₁ O ₂ NCl ₂	—	—	75

TABLE I (contd.).

Amide.	Mol. prop. of amide to SO ₂ Cl ₂ .	Product.	M. p.	Formula.	Analysis Found.	Analysis Req.	Yield
Salicyl- <i>m</i> -toluidide	1 : 4	(i) 3 : 5-Dichlorosalicyl-4' : 6'-dichloro- <i>m</i> -toluidide (B)	214-15°	C ₁₄ H ₁₀ O ₂ NC ₂ Cl ₄	Cl, 38.7% Cl, 38.9%	Cl, 38.9%	10%
Salicyl- <i>p</i> -toluidide	1 : 1	(ii) 5-Chlorosalicyl-6'-chloro- <i>m</i> -toluidide*	221-22°	C ₁₄ H ₁₁ O ₂ NC ₂	—	—	50
Salicyl- <i>p</i> -toluidide	1 : 2	5-Chlorosalicyl- <i>p</i> -toluidide (C)	216-17°	C ₁₄ H ₁₃ O ₂ NC ₂	13.3	13.3	30
Salicyl- <i>p</i> -toluidide	1 : 4	5-Chlorosalicyl- <i>p</i> -toluidide*	216°	C ₁₄ H ₁₃ O ₂ NC ₂	—	—	60
Salicyl- <i>p</i> -toluidide	1 : 4	(i) 3 : 5-Dichlorosalicyl-3'-chloro- <i>p</i> -toluidide (B & D)	164-65°	C ₁₄ H ₁₀ O ₂ NC ₃	31.9	32.2	20
<i>o</i> -Methoxybenzanilide	1 : 1	(ii) 5-Chlorosalicyl- <i>p</i> -toluidide*	215-16°	C ₁₄ H ₁₂ O ₂ NC ₂	—	—	50
<i>o</i> -Methoxybenz- <i>o</i> -anisidide	1 : 1	<i>o</i> -Methoxybenz-4-chloroanisidide (B & D)	75-76°	C ₁₄ H ₁₂ O ₂ NC ₂	13.8	13.6	60
<i>o</i> -Toluanilide	1 : 1	<i>o</i> -Methoxybenz-5-chloro- <i>o</i> -anisidide (B)	135-36°	C ₁₅ H ₁₄ O ₂ NC ₂	12.4	12.2	60
<i>o</i> -Toluanilide	1 : 2	(i) <i>o</i> -Tolu-2 : 4-dichloroanisidide (B & D)	133-34°	C ₁₄ H ₁₂ ONCl	14.3	14.5	—
<i>o</i> -Toluanilide	1 : 2	(ii) <i>o</i> -Tolu-4-chloroanisidide*	128°	C ₁₄ H ₁₁ ONCl ₂	25.1	25.3	70
<i>o</i> -Tolu- <i>o</i> -toluidide	1 : 1	<i>o</i> -Tolu-5-chloro- <i>o</i> -toluidide (B & D)	132-33°	C ₁₄ H ₁₂ ONCl	—	—	—
<i>o</i> -Tolu- <i>m</i> -toluidide	1 : 1	<i>o</i> -Tolu-4 : 6-dichloro- <i>m</i> -toluidide (B & D)	182°	C ₁₅ H ₁₄ ONCl	13.4	13.7	70
<i>o</i> -Tolu- <i>p</i> -toluidide	1 : 1	<i>o</i> -Tolu-3-chloro- <i>p</i> -toluidide (B & D)	120-21°	C ₁₅ H ₁₆ ONCl ₂	23.9	24.1	—
<i>o</i> -Chlorobenzanilide	1 : 1	<i>o</i> -Chlorobenz-4-chloroanisidide (A & D)	119-20°	C ₁₅ H ₁₁ ONCl	13.5	13.7	—
<i>o</i> -Chlorobenz- <i>m</i> -chloroanisidide	1 : 1	<i>o</i> -Chlorobenz-3 : 4-dichloroanisidide (B)	119-20°	C ₁₅ H ₉ ONCl ₂	26.5	26.7	80
<i>o</i> -Chlorobenz- <i>m</i> -chloroanisidide	1 : 1	<i>o</i> -Chlorobenz-3 : 4-dichloroanisidide (B)	143°	C ₁₅ H ₉ ONCl ₃	35.2	35.4	—

N.B.—(i) In the case of toluidides and anisidide Me and OMe are numbered 1.

(ii) Substances marked * were identified by mixed m.p. with authentic specimens.

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